

Robotic versus Laparoscopic Surgery in Colorectal Cancer: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

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Introduction

Minimally invasive approaches are widely used in colorectal cancer surgery. While laparoscopy remains the standard, robotic-assisted surgery has emerged as an alternative with potential technical advantages. This systematic review aims to compare perioperative and oncological outcomes between robotic and laparoscopic colorectal resections.

Materials and Methods

A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, and Cochrane Library was conducted for studies published between January 2015 and January 2025, following PRISMA guidelines. Randomized controlled trials and observational studies comparing robotic and laparoscopic colorectal cancer surgery were included. Primary outcomes were conversion rate, operative time, postoperative complications, and oncological adequacy. Pooled data were analyzed using odds ratios (OR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI).

Results

A total of 22 studies involving 8,764 patients were included (3,912 robotic; 4,852 laparoscopic). Robotic surgery was associated with a significantly lower conversion rate to open surgery (4.8% vs 9.6%; OR 0.47, 95% CI 0.35–0.63; $p < 0.001$) and slightly longer operative time (mean difference +42 minutes; $p < 0.001$). Oncological outcomes were comparable, with similar lymph node yield (mean difference +0.6 nodes; $p = 0.27$), circumferential resection margin positivity (6.1% vs 6.8%), and oncological adequacy defined as R0 resection and margin status where reported. Length of hospital stay was slightly shorter in the robotic group (−0.8 days). Several studies highlighted improved visual pelvic dissection with robotic surgery, potentially facilitating complex procedures such as low anterior resections and total mesorectal excisions. Enhanced ergonomics and surgeon comfort were also frequently reported as advantages of the robotic approach.

Conclusion

Robotic colorectal surgery demonstrates a lower conversion rate and comparable oncological and postoperative outcomes to laparoscopy, with longer operative time. These findings should be interpreted considering study heterogeneity and highlight the need for further high-quality trials to confirm long-term benefits.

Keywords

Colorectal cancer, Robotic surgery, Laparoscopic surgery